

VIRTUALNA VADBA KOT TREND PRIHODNOSTI: POTROŠNIŠKE NAVADE IN IZZIVI FITNES INDUSTRIJE

Aleksandra Klampfer Žičkar <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4634-6458>³

Tina Vukasović <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1434-5291>⁴

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Povzetek

Namen: Namen raziskave je preučiti potrošniško vedenje v kontekstu virtualnih fitnes storitev in identificirati ključne dejavnike, ki vplivajo na sprejemanje, uporabo ter zaznana vrednost vadbe na daljavo. Poseben poudarek je na razumevanju motivacije, zadovoljstva in pričakovanj uporabnikov ter na prepoznavanju razlogov, zakaj se nekateri potrošniki ne odločijo za uporabo virtualnih programov.

Metodologija: Raziskava temelji na kvantitativnem pristopu z uporabo spletnega anketnega vprašalnika. Preučevane so bile demografske značilnosti, pogostost uporabe, motivacijski dejavniki, zaznana vrednost ter stopnja zadovoljstva z virtualnimi vadbami. Za obdelavo podatkov smo uporabili opisno statistiko, test zanesljivosti in izbrane neparametrične statistične metode, s katerimi smo preverili povezanosti med ključnimi spremenljivkami.

Ugotovitve: Rezultati kažejo, da virtualne vadbe ponujajo visoko raven fleksibilnosti, dostopnosti in raznolikosti programov, kar pomembno prispeva k pozitivni uporabniški izkušnji. Uporabniki cenijo možnost vadbe doma, prihranek časa ter enostavno vključevanje vadbe v natrpane urnike. Socialna interakcija s trenerjem ostaja pomemben motivacijski dejavnik, medtem ko neuporabniki kot ključni razlog za neuporabo navajajo dvome o učinkovitosti in pomanjkanje osebnega stika.

Omejitev: Raziskavo omejuje majhen in geografsko omejen vzorec ter uporaba spletnega anketiranja, kar lahko vpliva na reprezentativnost rezultatov.

Praktične in/ali družbene posledice: Ugotovitve prispevajo k razvoju hibridnih vadbenih modelov, ki združujejo prednosti virtualne in tradicionalne vadbe. Fitnes centri, trenerji in razvijalci digitalnih platform lahko na podlagi rezultatov izboljšajo prilagodljivost, kakovost in učinkovitost storitev ter okrepijo uporabniško izkušnjo.

Izvirnost: Izvirnost prispevka je v povezovanju teoretičnih spoznanj s celovito empirično analizo vedenja uporabnikov virtualnih vadb. Raziskava ponuja poglobljen vpogled v dinamiko digitalizirane fitnes industrije ter prispeva k razumevanju dejavnikov, ki oblikujejo uporabniško izkušnjo in prihodnji razvoj digitalnih vadbenih rešitev.

Ključne besede: vedenje potrošnikov, digitalna tehnologija, fitnes industrija, virtualna vadba.

³ International School for Social and Business Studies, Mariborska cesta 7, 3000 Celje, Slovenia; sancikz@gmail.com.

⁴ International School for Social and Business Studies, Mariborska cesta 7, 3000 Celje, Slovenia; tina.vukasovic@mfdps.si.

VIRTUAL WORKOUTS AS A TREND OF THE FUTURE: CONSUMER HABITS AND CHALLENGES FOR THE FITNESS INDUSTRY

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to examine consumer behaviour in the context of virtual fitness services and to identify the key factors that influence the acceptance, use, and perceived value of remote workout programmes. Special emphasis is placed on understanding users' motivation, satisfaction, and expectations, as well as on identifying the reasons why some consumers choose not to use virtual fitness programmes.

Methodology: The research is based on a quantitative approach using an online survey questionnaire. The study examined demographic characteristics, frequency of use, motivational factors, perceived value, and user satisfaction with virtual workouts. Descriptive statistics, reliability testing, and selected non-parametric methods were used to analyse the relationships between key variables.

Results: The results show that virtual workouts offer a high level of flexibility, accessibility, and programme diversity, all of which significantly contribute to a positive user experience. Users value the ability to exercise at home, save time, and easily incorporate workouts into busy schedules. Social interaction with the trainer remains an important motivational factor, while non-users most often cite doubts about effectiveness and the lack of personal contact as reasons for not engaging in virtual workouts.

Research limitations: The study is limited by a small and geographically restricted sample and by the use of online data collection, which may affect the representativeness of the results.

Practical and/or Social implications: The findings support the development of hybrid workout models that combine the advantages of virtual and traditional training. Fitness centres, trainers, and digital platform developers can use the results to improve the flexibility, quality, and effectiveness of their services and to enhance the overall user experience.

Originality: The originality of the study lies in its integration of theoretical insights with a comprehensive empirical analysis of virtual workout users' behaviour. The research provides an in-depth understanding of the dynamics of the digitalised fitness industry and contributes to the knowledge of factors shaping the user experience and the future development of digital workout solutions.

Keywords: consumer behavior, digital technology, fitness industry, virtual workout.

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Corresponding Author: Tina Vukasović, tina.vukasovic@mf dps.si

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Introduction

The virtual fitness industry is part of the broader field of consumer services, where changes in consumer behavior strongly influence the development of offerings. Purchase decisions are shaped by cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors that structure the decision-making process from need recognition to post-purchase behavior. Understanding these factors enables companies to design effective marketing strategies and adapt to the needs of modern users.

In the virtual fitness industry, price, accessibility, service quality, flexibility, and personal values related to a healthy lifestyle are particularly important in consumers' decisions. The development of digital platforms and wearable devices enables personalization, progress tracking, and the ability to exercise anytime and anywhere, which increases user satisfaction. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated growth while highlighting challenges such as digital literacy, equitable access, and the long-term adaptation of offerings.

The research problem of the article focuses on understanding consumer behavior in the use of virtual workout platforms. The aim is to examine the factors influencing their decisions and show how companies can develop sustainable solutions through appropriate knowledge management - solutions that foster satisfaction, motivation, and long-term user loyalty.

Purchase factors

A broad set of factors influences consumer decisions, together shaping a complex decision-making process. Understanding these factors allows companies to tailor strategies to consumer needs and desires, while trends, technological progress, and economic conditions also play an important role.

Demographic factors include age, gender, income, education, and family status. Younger buyers tend to favor novelty; older buyers focus more on utility. Higher income drives the selection of premium products, while limited resources encourage more rational choices. Education affects the criticality and information level of consumers. **Psychological factors** encompass motivation, perception, learning, and attitudes. Positive brand experiences increase the likelihood of repeat purchases, while personal beliefs and values strongly guide consumer preferences. **Sociocultural factors** arise from family, friends, social groups, and cultural norms. Social status and the desire for belonging influence brand choice, while cultural values guide purchasing habits across different environments. **Economic factors** determine purchasing power and consumer behavior. Economic conditions, inflation, unemployment, and interest rates directly affect the scope and type of consumption.

Technological factors include advances in digital platforms, mobile apps, and artificial intelligence, which are changing how consumers search for information, compare, and purchase products. **Personal factors** relate to personality, lifestyle, and individual preferences. Consumers often choose products that express their identity and life values.

The emergence of the virtual fitness industry

In recent years, the virtual fitness industry has experienced exceptional growth driven by digitalization, busy schedules, increased attention to health, and the coronavirus pandemic. New forms of exercise have emerged - from virtual marathons to guided online programs - while technological progress enables access without the need for expensive equipment. Mobile apps, online courses, and live-streamed workouts have become an affordable alternative to traditional exercise formats, offering flexibility and a wide range of programs (Zupančič, 2016; Vučković, 2017). During the COVID-19 pandemic, development accelerated further as gym closures and social restrictions spurred a shift to online workouts. Virtual platforms offered diverse programs - from yoga and Pilates to high-intensity training - mitigating users' psychological and physical challenges (Vučković, 2017; Ule, 2013). A key aspect of this industry is its social component. Through forums, social networks, and remote group classes, communities are built in which users share experiences, motivate each other, and often form lasting ties. Thus, the article highlights that the virtual fitness industry brings not only more accessible exercise but also an intertwining of health, social life, and technological progress (University of Maribor, 2018; Ricci et al., 2020).

Development of the virtual fitness industry

The industry's development is dynamic, based on technological innovation, changes in consumer habits, and health & wellness trends. Initially, virtual workouts consisted of simple videos consumers followed at home. With the spread of the internet and smart devices, interactive platforms, apps, online courses, and live streams emerged, greatly increasing accessibility and variety (Novak, 2014). External factors - especially COVID-19 - also influenced development; gym closures spurred a mass shift to online exercise. Sports brands like Nike and Adidas quickly adapted their strategies and offered online programs and events, accelerating market growth (Grand View Research, 2023). Historically, the 1990s were dominated by aerobic and Pilates video programs aimed at home workouts. With the internet's expansion in the early 2000s, online portals enabled wider access and more technique options, and with smartphones, mobile apps

became a key channel for exercising anytime and anywhere (Fidler, 2015; Di Vaio et al., 2021). The year 2020 saw a boom in live online workouts, providing users with an interactive experience and a sense of community. After the pandemic, virtual workouts became a stable segment, often combined with hybrid models that merge in-person training with digital accessibility (Vujičić, 2021; WellHub, 2023). The article thus emphasizes that virtual fitness is a high-quality alternative to traditional forms and remains an important part of the industry's future.

Advantages and challenges of remote workouts

Remote exercise brings many advantages but also challenges that shape the experience of consumers and companies in the virtual fitness industry. Key advantages include **flexibility** and **accessibility**. Users can exercise anytime and anywhere - especially important for workers, parents, and those with packed schedules. Financial accessibility also matters: many platforms offer free or affordable programs with varied styles. The virtual environment can gradually reduce stress and increase beginners' confidence, as they can train without feeling judged. Time is saved by eliminating commutes to gyms, which increases workout consistency. Social media, group classes, and forums create a sense of community and encourage motivation (Woodruff et al., 2021; Yang, 2023; Ricci et al., 2020). Challenges include **lack of personal supervision**, which can lead to exercise mistakes, injuries, and dissatisfaction with results. There is also a risk of declining motivation due to the absence of personal interaction and external oversight, requiring greater self-discipline. **Technology issues** - unstable connections, app glitches, and limited access to suitable equipment - can reduce engagement and lead to dropout (Molanorouzi et al., 2015; Guthold et al., 2018; Fortune Business Insights, 2023). Overall, remote workouts have great potential, but success depends on balancing advantages and challenges and adapting to the needs of different user groups.

The virtual fitness market includes multiple platforms with different programs and approaches tailored to user needs. They differ in scope, features, and training style so individuals can choose what suits them best. The article highlights several well-known examples:

- **Peloton** set new standards with live cycling classes offering an interactive experience and a sense of community. It also includes running, strength training, and stretching.
- **Beachbody On Demand** is known for intense programs like P90X and Insanity, with periodization and nutrition guidance; the platform is holistic and accessible across devices.
- **Nike Training Club** offers a wide range of workouts - from short to long, from strength to rehab. It includes video demonstrations, individual tailoring, and access to trainers to improve safety and effectiveness.
- **Fitbod** specializes in weight training. Based on goals, available equipment, and progress, it designs individualized programs and enables on-the-fly adjustments.
- **Zombies, Run!** blends exercise and gaming, placing users in a survival story where running or walking becomes part of a mission - boosting motivation and attracting fans of interactive challenges.
- **Strava** is a leading app for tracking running and cycling. Using GPS, it allows performance analysis and strengthens competitiveness and community.
- **Hard To Kill** is a specialized app for military-style preparation, combining strength, endurance, and mental readiness, aimed at a narrower user group.

Together, these platforms confirm the diversity and innovation of the virtual fitness industry, which merges technological progress, accessibility, and social aspects of exercise. This combination enables long-term growth and popularization of remote workouts.

Methods

Methodology and sample

A **quantitative research design** was applied to investigate consumer behavior in the use of virtual fitness platforms. The target population consisted of adults engaged in sports activities who had experience with online fitness programs. Efforts were made to capture diversity in terms of **age, gender, and education**.

Data were collected using an **online questionnaire** created in the 1ka survey platform. The questionnaire was published on **9 February 2025** and remained open until **21 March 2025**. The survey was distributed via **social networks** (Facebook, Instagram) and **private messages**, with the majority of responses obtained through social media channels.

Prior to full implementation, the questionnaire was **pilot-tested** on a sample of five individuals to verify clarity and appropriateness. Based on their feedback, several items were refined, and the final version was prepared.

A total of **100 respondents** participated in the study, comprising **38 men (38%)** and **62 women (62%)**. The predominance of women reflects their more frequent engagement in online fitness programs and their higher representation on social media platforms used for data collection. From a sociological perspective, women more often rely on virtual workouts due to the need to balance family and professional obligations.

Table 1: Respondent gender distribution

Gender	Number	Percent
Male	38	38 %
Female	62	62 %

The **age distribution** was as follows: 18–25 years (27%), 26–30 years (17%), 31–35 years (5%), 36–45 years (16%), and 46 years or older (35%).

Table 2: Respondent age distribution

Age group	Number	Percent
18 –25 years	27	27 %
26 –30 years	17	17 %
31 –35 years	5	5 %
36 –45 years	16	16 %
46 + years	35	35 %

The **educational structure** of respondents included: elementary education (6%), secondary education (38%), college/university degree (38%), and master’s degree (18%).

Table 3: Respondent education distribution

Education	Number	Percent
Elementary school	6	6 %
Secondary school	38	38 %
College/University	38	38 %
Master's degree	18	18 %

The dataset was analyzed using **descriptive statistics** to summarize demographic characteristics and patterns of use. To test research hypotheses, **reliability analysis (Cronbach’s alpha)** was employed, followed by the **Kolmogorov–Smirnov test** to examine distribution normality and **Spearman’s correlation coefficients** to assess relationships between variables.

Results and discussion

Frequency of using online workout platforms

Respondents reported varying levels of engagement with online workout platforms. A total of 21% indicated that they had never used such platforms, while 35% reported rare use, defined as once per month. Occasional use, defined as more than twice per month, was reported by 20% of respondents. Regular users, who trained at least once per week, represented 13% of the sample, and 11% reported frequent use, defined as more than three times per week. These findings suggest that while a considerable proportion of respondents are not active users, the survey still captures the perspective of both users and non-users. This dual perspective is valuable, as it highlights areas where virtual platforms could improve their reach and attract new participants.

Table 4: Frequency of using virtual workout platforms

How often do you use virtual workout platforms?	Number	Percent
Never	21	21 %
Rarely (once per month)	35	35 %
Occasionally (more than twice per month)	20	20 %
Regularly (once per week)	13	13 %
Frequently (more than three times per week)	11	11 %

Usage history of online platforms

Respondents were divided into four groups based on the length of their use of virtual workout platforms. A total of 42% reported using platforms for less than six months, 16% had been using them between six months and one year, 15% between one and two years, and 27% had been engaged with such platforms for more than two years.

This distribution shows that the majority of respondents were relatively new users, while more than a quarter had long-term experience. The presence of both short-term and long-term users in the sample provides valuable insights into differences in satisfaction, motivation, and training outcomes.

Table 4: Usage history of online platforms

How long have you used virtual workout platforms?	Number	Percent
Less than 6 months	42	42 %
6 months to 1 year	16	16 %
1 –2 years	15	15 %
More than 2 years	27	27 %

Satisfaction with fitness since using virtual platforms

When asked about their satisfaction with physical fitness since starting to use virtual workout platforms, 40% of respondents reported being satisfied or very satisfied, while 27% were dissatisfied or very dissatisfied. A total of 33% remained neutral. These results indicate that experiences with virtual workouts are not uniform. While a notable share of users reports positive effects, more than a quarter express dissatisfaction, and one-third have not formed a clear opinion. This suggests that virtual platforms hold potential for improvement in terms of program quality, guidance, and long-term user engagement.

Table 6: Satisfaction with physical fitness since using virtual workout platforms

How satisfied are you with your physical fitness since using virtual workout platforms?	Number	Percent
Very dissatisfied or dissatisfied	27	27 %
Neutral	33	33 %
Satisfied or very satisfied	40	40 %

Comparing current fitness levels with the period before virtual workouts

Respondents were asked to compare their current physical fitness with the period before they started using virtual workout platforms. A total of 32% reported an improvement, 29% observed a decline, and 39% stated that their fitness level had not changed. These findings indicate that the effectiveness of virtual workouts varies considerably among users. While almost one-third experienced positive changes, a similar proportion noticed a decline. The high share of respondents reporting no change suggests that the outcomes of virtual training strongly depend on individual expectations, workout consistency, and program quality.

Table 7: Comparison of physical condition before and after using virtual workout platforms

How would you rate your physical condition compared to the period before using virtual workout platforms?	Number	Percent
Improvement	32	32 %
No change	39	39 %
Decline	29	29 %

Perception of contribution of virtual workouts to fitness

Respondents were asked whether they believe that virtual workouts contribute to their physical fitness. A total of 43% agreed, 32% disagreed, and 25% remained neutral. These results suggest that while nearly half of the respondents perceive a positive contribution, a significant share either disagrees or is undecided. The relatively high proportion of neutral responses points to uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of virtual platforms, indicating the need for improvements in program quality and persuasiveness.

Table 8: Perception of contribution of virtual workouts to fitness

Do you agree that virtual workouts contribute to your physical fitness?	Number	Percent
Agree	43	43 %
Neutral	25	25 %

Disagree	32	32 %
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Personalized programs and motivation

Several questions addressed the role of individualized programs in shaping user motivation and training outcomes. According to the results, 54% of respondents stated that individualized programs increased their motivation, while 49% believed that such programs improved their results. About one quarter disagreed, and roughly one third remained neutral. When asked about additional motivation provided by personalized programs, 50% reported a positive effect, 31% were neutral, and around 19% experienced no change. These results indicate that personalization is generally perceived as beneficial, especially in terms of motivation, though not all respondents recognize clear improvements. The presence of neutral and skeptical responses highlights the need for further development of tailored programs and better communication of their benefits.

Table 9: Questions on individualized programs and motivation

Question	1		2		3		4		5	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Do you feel that individualized ...	10	10 %	12	12 %	24	24 %	29	29 %	25	25 %
How would you rate the effect of individualized programs ...	6	6 %	14	14 %	31	31 %	28	28 %	21	21 %
How much additional motivation do you feel ...	7	7 %	12	12 %	31	31 %	30	30 %	20	20 %

Comparison of live and virtual workouts

The comparison between live and virtual sessions revealed divided preferences. A total of 33% of respondents preferred live workouts, 38% preferred virtual workouts, and 29% remained neutral. When asked specifically about trainer interaction, 50% of respondents reported that this was the main reason for choosing live workouts. In contrast, 26% disagreed with this statement, and 24% were neutral. Further, 45% of respondents believed that virtual workouts cannot fully replace live ones, 23% disagreed, and 32% were undecided. These results highlight ambivalence: while virtual formats offer flexibility and accessibility, many users continue to value interpersonal contact and the social aspects of in-person exercise.

Table 10: Comparison of preferences for live and virtual workouts

Question	1		2		3		4		5	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
How much more do you prefer live workouts compared to ...	26	26 %	7	7 %	29	29 %	17	17 %	21	21 %
Do you prefer to attend live workouts because of the interaction ...	16	16 %	10	10 %	24	24 %	16	16 %	34	34 %
Do you think that virtual workouts do not ...	11	11 %	12	12 %	32	32 %	24	24 %	21	21 %

Flexibility of virtual workout platforms

Flexibility was addressed with three specific questions. Almost half of the respondents (46%) reported that they often or always use virtual platforms to adapt workouts to their lifestyle, while 33% rarely or never used them for this purpose. When asked whether virtual workouts are better tailored to individual needs compared to traditional ones, 38% agreed, 27% disagreed, and 35% remained neutral. Finally, 48% of respondents indicated that they would use virtual workouts more often if platforms offered greater flexibility. A total of 26% would not increase their use, and another 26% were undecided. These findings confirm that flexibility is a decisive factor in motivating broader and more frequent use of virtual platforms.

Table 11: Flexibility of virtual workout platforms

Question	1		2		3		4		5	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
How often do you use platforms for ...	16	16 %	17	17 %	21	21 %	24	24 %	22	22 %

Do you think that virtual workouts are better tailored to your ...	12	12 %	15	15 %	35	35 %	22	22 %	16	16 %
Would you use more virtual workouts ...	10	10 %	16	16 %	26	26 %	25	25 %	23	23 %

Interaction and feedback

The last group of questions focused on interaction with trainers and the role of personalized feedback. A total of 45% of respondents rated knowledge sharing with trainers as effective, 22% found it ineffective, and 33% remained neutral. When asked about the effect of personalized feedback, 61% of respondents stated that it increased their engagement, 12% disagreed, and 27% were neutral. Finally, 36% reported that interaction with trainers led to long-term improvements, while 33% disagreed and 31% were neutral. These findings underline the importance of professional support and feedback for maintaining motivation and achieving sustainable progress in virtual workouts.

Table 12: Interaction with trainers and personalized feedback

Question	1		2		3		4		5	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
How would you rate the effectiveness of knowledge sharing ...	8	8 %	14	14 %	33	33 %	29	29 %	16	16 %
Do you think that personalized feedback from ...	3	3 %	9	9 %	27	27 %	34	34 %	27	27 %
Have you noticed improvements in ...	11	11 %	22	22 %	31	31 %	25	25 %	11	11 %

Overall, the results reveal a divided perception of virtual workouts: on the one hand, positive effects of personalization, flexibility, and motivation; on the other hand, persistent distrust compared to live sessions and a high share of neutral responses, pointing to the need for further development and stronger evidence of the effectiveness of virtual platforms.

Hypotheses testing

To test the hypotheses, Cronbach’s alpha was used to assess reliability, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test to examine distribution normality, and Spearman’s correlation coefficients to analyze relationships between variables.

H1: Users who regularly use virtual workout platforms report greater satisfaction with their fitness and better physical condition.

The analysis was conducted on a subgroup of 13 regular users (13 % of the total sample). Cronbach’s alpha reached 0.821, which indicates good reliability.

Table 13: Results of Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Spearman tests for H1

Question	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (p, σ , D)			Spearman (p, σ , r)		
	p	σ	D	p	σ	r
Satisfaction...	0.532	0.949	0.204	0.529	0.933	0.222
Physical condition...	0.520	1.089	0.206	0.498	1.034	0.209

Since p-values exceeded 0.05 in both cases, the results cannot be generalized to the entire population. The small subgroup size and high standard deviation contributed to this limitation.

Conclusion: H1 is partially confirmed. Virtual platforms may contribute to satisfaction and physical condition, but the evidence remains limited.

H2: Individualized programs on virtual platforms significantly increase motivation for regular exercise and improve results.

The analysis included gender as a correlate. Cronbach’s alpha reached 0.904, confirming high reliability.

Table 14: Results of Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Spearman tests for H2

Question	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (p, σ, D)			Spearman (p, σ, r)		
	p	σ	D	p	σ	r
Individualized programs increase motivation...	0.026	1.305	0.202	0.071	1.024	0.231
Effect on results...	0.044	1.234	0.244	0.024	1.119	0.198

With $p \leq 0.05$ in most cases and a sufficiently large sample, the results are statistically significant. **Conclusion:** H2 is confirmed. Individualized programs positively affect both motivation and results.

H3: *Users prefer to remain loyal to in-person workouts.*

Gender was used as a correlate. Cronbach’s alpha reached 0.886, indicating good reliability.

Table 15: Results of Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Spearman tests for H3

Question	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (p, σ, D)			Spearman (p, σ, r)		
	p	σ	D	p	σ	r
Preference for in-person workouts...	0.013	1.483	0.185	0.039	1.392	0.217

Both tests yielded $p < 0.05$, which indicates statistical significance and allows generalization to the sample. **Conclusion:** H3 is confirmed. Despite the growth of virtual platforms, loyalty to in-person workouts remains strong, primarily due to trainer interaction.

H4: *Younger users (18–35) use virtual platforms more often because they better fit their lifestyle.*

Age group 18–35 was used as a correlate. Cronbach’s alpha reached 0.787, which is within the acceptable range.

Table 16: Results of Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Spearman tests for H4

Question	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (p, σ, D)			Spearman (p, σ, r)		
	p	σ	D	p	σ	r
Frequency due to lifestyle fit...	0.043	1.225	0.194	0.082	1.303	0.245

The results were partially significant, but the high variability within the subgroup limits generalization. **Conclusion:** H4 is conditionally confirmed. Flexibility is attractive to younger users, but subgroup heterogeneity prevents strong conclusions.

H5: *Platforms that effectively facilitate knowledge exchange between users and trainers and provide personalized feedback increase user engagement and improve long-term results.*

Gender was used as a correlate. Cronbach’s alpha reached 0.872, confirming good reliability.

Table 17: Results of Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Spearman tests for H5

Question	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (p, σ, D)			Spearman (p, σ, r)		
	p	σ	D	p	σ	r
Knowledge exchange effectiveness...	0.002	1.023	0.296	0.011	1.112	0.323
Long-term improvements noticed...	0.009	1.089	0.277	0.018	1.208	0.299

Since all p -values are < 0.05 , the results can be generalized to the entire sample.

Conclusion: H5 is confirmed. Knowledge exchange and personalized feedback increase engagement and contribute to long-term improvements.

Conclusion

In modern society, digitalization strongly influences the fitness industry. This article examined consumer behavior in the context of virtual fitness services and the future development of remote workouts. The theoretical part discussed key concepts and market dynamics, where consumers are increasingly moving away from traditional in-person formats. In the empirical part, we conducted a survey among users and non-users of virtual services, analyzing their habits, preferences, and satisfaction levels. The results show that users are mostly satisfied with remote workouts because they allow flexibility, accessibility, and a wide selection of programs, which is especially important for individuals with busy schedules.

Understanding the needs, challenges, and preferences of users in the virtual fitness industry is crucial for designing effective training solutions that adapt to the modern lifestyle. Virtual platforms enable exercise for a wider group of people, regardless of time or location, and their long-term success depends on high-quality user experience, personalization, and technological improvements that support motivation and satisfaction.

The analysis showed that usage patterns vary widely. While a considerable proportion of respondents are regular or occasional users, a significant share remain non-users, indicating that the potential of virtual platforms is far from fully realized. Younger users appear more open to adopting digital formats, primarily because of the flexibility they provide, although this trend is not uniform across all age groups.

The findings also suggest that personalization is one of the most valued features of virtual platforms, as individualized programs were strongly linked to increased motivation and perceived effectiveness. However, trainer interaction and feedback remain crucial: many respondents emphasized that the absence of direct social contact is a major limitation of virtual workouts, and nearly half believe that digital formats cannot fully replace in-person training.

The hypotheses testing further confirmed that while virtual platforms can positively influence satisfaction, motivation, and long-term results, these effects are not equally distributed across all users. Individual characteristics, prior training habits, and expectations play an important role in shaping outcomes.

In conclusion, virtual workouts represent a promising complement to traditional fitness practices rather than a complete substitute. For sustainable growth, platforms must enhance flexibility, improve personalization, and incorporate mechanisms for meaningful interaction with trainers. Future research should explore hybrid models that combine the convenience of virtual platforms with the motivational and social benefits of in-person training, as these may provide the most effective solution for diverse user needs.

Practical implications

The findings of this study provide several practical insights for fitness professionals and platform developers. First, personalization should remain a central feature, as individualized programs have been shown to significantly boost user motivation and perceived results. Second, platforms should invest in enhancing interaction with trainers, for example through live sessions, feedback systems, or hybrid models, since social contact remains a strong motivator. Finally, flexibility must be emphasized, particularly for younger users, who value the ability to adapt workouts to their lifestyles. By combining these elements—personalization, interaction, and flexibility—virtual platforms can expand their appeal and encourage long-term user engagement.

Limitations and future research

This study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample size was limited to 100 respondents, which restricts the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the sample was obtained through social media and online distribution, which may have introduced selection bias by favoring more digitally active individuals. The reliance on self-reported data also poses a risk of subjective bias in the responses.

Future research should therefore consider larger and more diverse samples, including users from different cultural and demographic backgrounds. Longitudinal studies would also provide deeper insights into how virtual workouts influence motivation, satisfaction, and fitness outcomes over time. Finally, further studies should investigate hybrid models that integrate virtual and live components, as these may prove to be the most effective solution for combining flexibility with interpersonal interaction.

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